

COMPARISON OF THE PROPERTIES OF POLYESTER-BASED POWDER COATINGS CONTAINING DIFFERENT CLAYS MODIFIED WITH 3-AMINOPROPYLTRIEHOXYSILANE

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ABSTRACT

Mineral clays such as montmorillonite are incorporated into polymer matrices to improve the mechanical properties and thermal barriers of polymer composites. To improve the interaction polymer-clay it is necessary to get organoclays. Ion exchange of inorganic cations present in the clay structure by cationic surfactants, such as quaternary ammonium salts, has been the most widely used method for this purpose. The functionalization of the clay with silane compounds has been employed in the modification of clays for producing polymer nanocomposites. This study investigated the effect of the incorporation of 4 wt% of three different mineral clays (MMT-15A, MMT-30B and MMT-Na⁺) functionalized with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (γ -APS) on the mechanical, morphological and corrosion protection properties of a polyester-based powder paint. The coatings were characterized by X-ray diffraction, thermogravimetric analysis, optical microscopy, gloss measurement, adhesion, impact resistance, flexibility, open circuit potential monitoring and immersion tests in saline solution. XDR results showed that it was not possible to produce nanocomposites, since no change of basal spacing was verified in the coatings containing clays functionalized with γ -APS compared to those with clays not functionalized. The presence of the clays reduced the maximum degradation temperature of the paint. Clay agglomerates were visualized nearly the coating surface. The clay-containing coating showed a reduction of brightness, and this effect was more pronounced for the coating containing the MMT-15A clay modified with silane. All coatings showed good adhesion to the metal substrate. However, coatings containing the S-MMT_{30B} and S-MMT_{15A} showed cracks and peeling when subjected to impact and flexibility test. It was found that the silane modified clays did not improve the corrosion performance of the neat coating.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer nanocomposites containing nanoclays have attracted great interest because they have better properties than the pure polymers such as reduction of the gas permeability (barrier properties) [1], flame retardancy [2], increased mechanical properties [3] and high corrosion performance [4-7], among others [8-9].

In their natural state the clays have hydrophilic character and low compatibility with the polymer, showing trend to agglomerate when dispersed in the polymer matrix. To improve the compatibility and dispersion of the clay in the matrix, clays must be organically modified. The most commonly used method for modifying the clay is the ion exchange of inorganic cations present in the clay structure by

cationic surfactants such as quaternary ammonium salts, which produce organoclays (OMMT) [10-11].

Several studies have been developed functionalizing the clay with silanes to increase the clay/polymer compatibility and also to provide functional groups in order to promote chemical bonds with the polymer.

Choi et al. [12] incorporated the montmorillonite clay (MMT) modified with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (γ -APS) silane in an epoxy matrix and by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis it was found that the modified clay with the silane restricted separation (exfoliation) of clay layers during the curing reaction. The authors found improved mechanical properties of the composite provided by the chemical interaction between the epoxy molecules and the amine groups of the functionalized clay. A similar result was observed by Spencer et al. [13] who added Cloisite®15A modified with trimethoxyphenylsilane in a polypropylene matrix. Wang et al. [14] found that the clay functionalized with γ -APS when incorporated into the epoxy matrix showed a high degree of exfoliation, generating a nanocomposite with improved thermal and mechanical properties. Shanmugaraj & Ryu [15] observed that the presence of MMT modified with the γ -APS in an epoxy-based nanocomposite resulted in better curing characteristics when compared to the pure epoxy matrix. Working with a similar system Bruce et al. [16] observed that the structure of the nanocomposite was not dependent on the silane functionality, but it affected the thermal and mechanical properties of the nanocomposite.

Piscitelli et al. [17] studied the effect of incorporating clay MMT- Na^+ modified with γ -APS or silane-N-(2-aminoethyl)-3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane in an epoxy resin using two different dispersion methods. Although they did not get the exfoliation of the clay in the polymer matrix, those composites showed better physical, thermal and mechanical properties in relation to the neat epoxy matrix and also to composites with not modified MMT. They concluded that chemical interactions between the epoxy matrix and the amino groups present in the modified clay had higher influence than the degree of exfoliation of the clay in the polymer matrix in the properties of the composites. A good dispersion of MMT modified with N-(2-aminoethyl)-3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane into epoxy resin was found by Silva et al. [18]. The binding of the epoxy group of the silane organic fraction contributed to reduce agglomerates (tactoids), providing delamination of the clay with silane incorporation into the clay galleries getting place to an exfoliated structure.

The incorporation of MMT organoclay (OMMT) modified with silane in a polymer matrix was also studied by many researchers. Mansoori et al. [19] incorporated different concentrations of Cloisite®20A modified with vinyltrichlorosilane in a polyacrylamide matrix. They observed that the incorporation up to 7 wt% resulted in the formation of exfoliated/interlayered structured nanocomposites with glass transition temperature (T_g) higher than the polymer. For higher concentrations they observed the formation of clay agglomerates which caused the reduction of T_g . Chen et al. [20-21] & Yoon and Chen [22] studied different OMMT modified with glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPTS) in poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA) matrix. Chen et al. [20-21] found that the modification of Cloisite®25A with silane was essential for obtaining an exfoliated structure. In addition, the nanocomposites showed high mechanical strength due to increased interaction between PLLA and the modified clay. In the study of Chen and Yoon [22] Cloisite®15A clays, Cloisite®20A or Cloisite®30B modified with silane showed that the intercalation of clays depends mainly on the organic compound used in ion exchange and the modification of the clay with silane did not contribute significantly to obtaining the interlayered or exfoliated structure.

This study aims to evaluate the effect of adding 4% wt of different clays (MMT- Na^+ , MMT-30B and MMT-15A) modified with γ -APS in the properties of a polyester-based coating applied on mild steel.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The materials used to accomplish the grafting reaction of the clay were montmorillonite Cloisite® Na^+ (MMT- Na^+), Cloisite®30B (MMT-30B) and Cloisite®15A (MMT-15A) provided by

Southern Clay Products, 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (γ -APS) with a purity of 99% provided by Aldrich Chemical Company and solvent ethanol P.A. from Vetec Fine Chemicals.

To obtain the powder coating it was used the polyester resin POLIDROX® RP3062 supplied by Polidrox Resins Ltda.; tiglicidiliscianurate curing agent (TGIC), supplied by Huntsman; spreading agent, ResiflowPV-60, provided by Estron Chemical Inc.; and benzoin provided by Datiquim Chemicals. The powder coatings were applied on AISI 1008 carbon steel panels with dimensions of 70 mm x 120 mm x 0,65 mm.

2.2 Modification of clays with silane

MMT-Na⁺, MMT-30B and MMT-15A clays were previously dried in an oven at 60 °C for about 24 hours. 10 g of γ -APS were dispersed in 200 mL of hydroalcoholic solution (75/25 v/v) and kept stirred until occur complete dispersion of the clay. In another container, 10 g of clay were dispersed in 300 mL of the same solution and stirred until complete dispersion of the clay. After that the solution containing silane was added to the suspension containing clay and this was kept magnetically stirred for 8 hours at 50 °C. The suspension was allowed to stand for 1 hour and the product was dried for 24 hours at 60 °C. Silane modified MMT were designated as S-MMT_{Na}, S-MMT_{30B} and S-MMT_{15A} related to MMT-Na⁺, MMT-30B and MMT-15A, respectively.

2.3 Preparation of polyester-based powder coatings

The powder coating formulation was based on a commercial polyester powder varnish without clay, named TP/0, and containing 4 wt% of S-MMT_{Na}, S-MMT_{30B} and S-MMT_{15A}, named TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and TP/4/SMMT_{15A}, respectively.

S-MMT clays were dried in an oven at 60 °C for 8 hours before to be mixed with other components of the paint and further processed in a co-rotating double-screw extrusion (MH Equipamentos Ltda, model MH-COR LAB, L/D 32, diameter of thread 20 mm) at 200 rpm and 90 °C. The extruded material was manually leveled and chipped before grounding in a knife mill and sieved to 200 mesh sieve (aperture of 75 μ m).

The powder paint was applied on carbon steel panels using an electrostatic spray corona gun from TCA Eco Tecnoadvance. The powder coatings were cured in oven for 20 minutes at 200 °C.

2.4 Characterization

The coatings were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using the Shimadzu-XRD 6000 diffractometer, using Cu-K α as source for generating X-rays. The diffraction angle of 2θ were scanned from 1° to 12° and the basal spacing was calculated by Bragg equation ($\lambda=2d\sin\theta$). Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed on Shimadzu TGA-50 equipment between 25 °C and 500 °C at a rate of 10 °C.min⁻¹ with nitrogen gas flow of 50 mL.min⁻¹ and from 500 °C to 800 °C in synthetic air atmosphere. Optical microscopy (OM) was done using the optical microscope by Nikon model Epiphot 200. Adhesion tape test was performed following ASTM D3359 – Method B. Flexibility was performed with a Byk Gardner conical mandrel according to ASTM D522. The impact resistance was performed with a Byk Gardner impact tester following ASTM D2794 using impact force of the 50 kg.cm. Gloss measurement (ASTM D523) employed a Konical Minolta gloss meter Multi Gloss 268 Plus. Open circuit potential monitoring (OCP) was performed in 3.5% (wt/v) NaCl solution for 76 days with a two-electrode system: the working electrode (sample) and the reference electrode (KCl saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and the values were recorded with a Minipa multimeter. For the immersion test a vertical incision was made on the painted panels previously they were immersed in NaCl for 42 days (1008 hours). The subcutaneous migration was measured according to ASTM D1654.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 X-ray diffraction

XDR diffractograms of the clays and of the powder coatings with 4 wt% of S-MMT_{Na}, S-MMT_{30B} or S-MMT_{15A} are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: XDR diffractograms of the no modified clays, silane modified clays and powder coatings containing (A) S-MMT_{Na}, (B) S-MMT_{30B} and (C) S-MMT_{15A}.

XRD results indicated that the polyester resin did not penetrate in the interlayer space of the clay since there was no significant change in the basal spacing in relation to those shown for the no modified clays. Thus the incorporation of the clays into the polyester matrix resulted in the formation of a microcomposite and not in a nanocomposite as expected.

The similar values for the basal spacing were found for the modified clays and for the composites with these indicate that the interaction between the clay and the resin occurred in the step of obtaining the nanocomposite and not in the curing step. Similar findings were reported by Malucelli et al. [23]

The incorporation of the silane in the clay structure may be promoting strong molecular interactions between the clay layers, preventing its exfoliation and/or intercalation of the polymer in the interlayer space of the modified clays. According to Su et al. [24] the modification of clay in silane-alcohol solution causes a blocking effect and the loss of the swelling property, preventing the exfoliation of the clay.

3.2 Thermogravimetric analysis

The thermal behavior of the powder coatings was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and thermograms are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Thermographs of (a) TGA e (b) DTG of the powder coatings.

The powder paint presented two mass loss events, the first event observed in inert atmosphere of N_2 and the second event corresponds to the effect of changing the atmosphere of the equipment to synthetic air, which accelerated the degradation process of the resin.

By TGA and DTG it was observed that the presence of silane modified MMT in the powder coatings reduced its maximum degradation temperature (T_{max}). TP/4/SMMT_{15A} showed T_{max} reduction of 9,2 °C compared to the T_{max} of TP/0, which can be attributed to the degradation of organic ions and silane present in the clay structure. Katsoulis et al. [25] attributed the poor chemical interaction/compatibility between the polymer matrix and the nanoparticle result to a weak surface adhesion and decreased thermal stability of nanocomposite.

3.3 Optical microscopy

The images of the coatings surface obtained by MO are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Optical micrografies of the coatings surface (A) TP/0 (B) TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, (C) TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and (D) TP/4/SMMT_{15A}. (50X)

The coatings containing clays presented agglomerates intercepting the coating surface. The coatings containing S-MMT_{30B} and S-MMT_{15A} presented higher agglomerate density but agglomerates of smaller size than that displayed on the coating with S-MMT_{Na}. Wang and Wang [2] and Saarivirta et al. [7] have found that the incorporation of high amounts of clay (> 1 wt%) causes

the formation of aggregates due to high surface energy of the clays, which prevent the dispersion of MMT in the polymer matrix.

3.4 Gloss measurement

Gloss measurements of the coatings are shown in Fig. 4. The incorporation of the clay in the paint formulation resulted in gloss reduction, which was more evident on TP/4/SMMT_{15A}. Nevertheless, based in industry standards, all coatings were classified as high-bright paints since that the values were above 80 U.B.

The reduction in the brightness observed is associated with the formation of clay agglomerates which reached the coating surface, increasing its roughness which is responsible for the diffuse reflection of incident light and consequently brightness reduction. Rissa et al. [26] and Jarnstron et al. [27] also observed reduction of the gloss of the organic coatings as a consequence of the surface roughness increasing. To Garea & Iovi [28] the brightness property depends strongly on the dispersion and stability of the fillers used in the paints. This last statement is corroborated by the poor dispersion (big agglomerates) observed for TP/4/S-MMT_{15A}.

Figure 4: Gloss values for the polyester-based coatings applied on carbon steel.

3.5 Adhesion test

All coatings showed good adhesion to the substrate and they were classified at grade 5B (0% of detachment) according to ASTM D3359-09. These results show that the incorporation of 4 wt% of the clays did not affect the adhesion properties of the coatings. Similar results were found by Piazza et al. [4] and Bagherzadeh & Mousavinejad [29] who studied the incorporation of MMT-Na⁺ and MMT-20B in an epoxy-based powder coating.

3.6 Impact resistance

The appearance of the coatings applied on carbon steel subjected to the impact test is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Images of the coatings surface (direct impact-above and reverse impact-bellow) after the impact test: (A) TP/0, (B) TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, (C) TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and (D) TP/4/SMMT_{15A}.

After visual examination of coatings subjected to impact test it was found that only the coating containing 4 wt% of clay S-MMT_{Na} showed no peeling or cracking. With the addition of 4 wt% of S-MMT_{30B} and S-MMT_{15A} it was observed the occurrence of cracks and peeling in both direct and reverse impact.

The presence of inorganic particles in the coating reduces the dissipation of energy after application of an external force causing fracture of the coating [30]. According to Dong et al. [3] large clay clumps can concentrate tensions around their edges and initiate the formation of cracks. The presence of smaller agglomerates increases the stress transfer to the matrix resulting in a larger amount of energy absorbed. Oliveira Jr. [31] found that the presence of particles in the polymer matrix results in heterogeneous systems under a stress effect of form regions of stress concentration causing local microcracks, with subsequent crack propagation. However, the author noted that the silane modified clay resulted in the presence of strong interactions at the interface, facilitating the transfer of stress between the polymer matrix and the reinforcing agent.

3.7 Flexibility

The appearance of the coatings TP/0, TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and TP/4/SMMT_{15A} applied on carbon steel subjected to the flexibility test are shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Appearance of the coated steel panels after the flexibility test: (A) TP/0, (B) TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, (C) TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and (D) TP/4/SMMT_{15A}.

For the coatings TP/0, TP/4/SMMT_{Na} and TP/4/SMMT_{30B} it was observed that when the coating was subjected to a slow deformation (adhesion and flexibility tests) the incorporated clay did not affect the performance of the paints, it means no defects on the paints after the tests. However, TP/4/SMMT_{15A} showed cracks in the highly deformed region. According to Piazza et al. [32] these

cracks can be related to the increase of coating stiffness imposed by the presence of clay in the polymer matrix.

3.8 Open circuit potential monitoring

Fig. 7 shows the behavior of the open circuit potential with time of coated carbon steel panels during exposure to NaCl solution.

For TP/0 it was not possible to measure the open circuit potential (OCP), since these coatings showed high resistance. The corrosion resistance of an organic coating without mainly defects depends on their barrier properties, i.e., the coating prevents the diffusion of corrosive ions and moisture through the film.

TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and TP/4/S-MMT_{15A} coatings showed a drop in OCP values after 50 days of immersion, being this potential close to the potential of the carbon steel (-648 mVSCE) and local corrosion was observed on the surface. After 41 days of storage was observed from the beginning reduction of OCP TP/4/SMMT_{Na} coating OCP reduced to -143.8 mVSCE.

Figure 7: Open circuit potential of the coated carbon steel: (A) TP/0, (B) TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, (C) TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and (D) TP/4/SMMT_{15A}.

According to Malucelli et al. [23] when a poor interaction between the nanoparticles and the polymer matrix interface can serve as a preferred route of diffusion of ions, thereby reducing the barrier properties of the nanocomposites compared with the clay-free coating. For them the best chemical interaction between the nanoparticles and the polymer matrix is due to the functionalization of clay, avoiding the discontinuity in the interface clay/polymer, resulting in increased corrosion protection coating.

For Nikraves et al. [33] the reduction of OCP value can be assigned to the hydrolytic degradation of the coating. When subjected to a high immersion time, the lining of the pores increase, resulting in a greater diffusion of the electrolyte interface coating/metal.

Visual assessment of coatings subjected to measurement of OCP was performed after 2400 hours of immersion (100 days of immersion). In Fig. 8 are shown surface aspects of carbon steel panels coated with powder paints after the immersion test in NaCl.

Figure 8: Appearance of the coated carbon steel panels: (A) TP/0, (B) TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, (C) TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and (D) TP/4/SMMT_{15A} after OCP measurement.

The visual analysis of the coatings after the immersion test did not reveal corrosion spots on the exposed region for the TP/0 and TP/4/SMMT_{Na} coatings. TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and TP/4/SMMT_{15A} showed some corrosion points, which were more visible in the coating containing S-MMT_{15A} clay.

3.9 Immersion tests

The coatings were immersed in dilute NaCl solution for 1008 hours. To assess migration subcutaneous it was held a vertical section in the central region of the specimens. The appearance of the coatings after 1008 hours of immersion is shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Appearance of the coated carbon steel panels: (A) TP/0, (B) TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, (C) TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and (D) TP/4/SMMT_{15A} after 1008 hours of immersion.

All coatings showed corrosion product in the incision. TP/4/SMMT_{15A} presented corrosion points on the coating surface. Subcutaneous migration was performed after of immersion to evaluate adhesion of the coating after the test. In Fig. 10 is shown the appearance of the coatings after subcutaneous migration.

Figure 10: Appearance of the coated carbon steel panels after evaluation of subcutaneous migration: (A) TP/0, (B) TP/4/SMMT_{Na}, (C) TP/4/SMMT_{30B} and (D) TP/4/SMMT_{15A}.

The presence of S-MMT_{30B} and S-MMT_{15A} clays on the polyester paint caused a major peeling of the coating in the area near the incision. Migration under coating film occurred TP/4/S-MMT_{30B} and TP/4/S-MMT_{15A}. Since the coating is disrupted, the clay particles are acting as points for facilitate the absorption and migration of electrolyte migration in the metal electrolyte interface with the coating.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Powder coatings were produced with MMT clays, functionalized with APS or not. XRD results did not confirmed the formation of nanocomposites since no change of basal spacing was verified for the coatings containing clays functionalized with APS compared to those with clays not functionalized. TP/4/SMMT_{15A} showed lower thermal stability than the others powder coatings. The presence of clay agglomerates was found nearly the coating surface and as a consequence the brightness was reduced. All coatings showed good adhesion to the metal substrate. However, coatings containing the S-MMT_{30B} and S-MMT_{15A} showed cracks and peeling when subjected to impact and flexibility test. It was found that the silane modified clays did not improve the corrosion performance of the neat coating.

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